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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Responsabilidad social de las empresas para con el trabajo sostenible y la confidencialidad de los empleados en las pequeñas y medianas empresas del Delta del Mekong (Vietnam)/DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8417569

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Resumen

El objetivo del estudio fue evaluar la influencia de la responsabilidad social de las empresas en el compromiso y la retención de empleados en las pequeñas y medianas empresas del delta del Mekong. Se recopilaron datos de 229 empleados de estas empresas. La investigación se llevó a cabo en dos fases: una cualitativa y otra cuantitativa. En la fase cualitativa, se seleccionaron 10 empleados y 10 directivos de empresas de la región para realizar entrevistas cara a cara, con una duración promedio de 45 minutos, desde febrero de 2023 hasta marzo de 2023. En la fase cuantitativa, se distribuyeron cuestionarios para una encuesta directa realizada desde el 1 de abril de 2023 hasta el 1 de mayo de 2023. Los investigadores utilizaron métodos de análisis de datos como la evaluación de la fiabilidad de la escala mediante el coeficiente Alfa de Cronbach, el análisis factorial exploratorio (EFA) y el análisis de modelos de regresión múltiple. Los resultados revelaron que hay dos componentes de la percepción de responsabilidad social de las empresas que influyen en el compromiso laboral de los empleados: la responsabilidad hacia el gobierno y la responsabilidad hacia los clientes, siendo la responsabilidad hacia el gobierno la de mayor influencia. Estos hallazgos proporcionan una base valiosa para que las pequeñas y medianas empresas en el delta del Mekong desarrollen estrategias de responsabilidad social que mejoren la lealtad, el compromiso y la retención de sus empleados. Esto, a su vez, ayuda a conservar los recursos humanos y mantener un rendimiento empresarial sostenible.

Palabras clave: Responsabilidad social; retención y compromiso de los empleados; pequeñas y medianas empresas; Delta del Mekong.

Abstract

Corporate Social Responsibility towards Sustainable Work and Employee Confidentiality in Small and Medium Enterprises in the Mekong Delta (Vietnam)

The aim of the study was to assess the influence of corporate social responsibility awareness on employee engagement and retention in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in the Mekong Delta. Data was collected from 229 employees working in SMEs. The research was conducted in two phases: qualitative research and quantitative research. In the qualitative research phase, the author employed a convenient sampling method, selecting 10 employees and 10 managerial executives from companies located in provinces and regions of the Mekong Delta. All interviews were conducted face-to-

face, with an average duration of 45 minutes. The interview period spanned from February 2023 to March 2023. In the quantitative research phase, data was collected through the distribution of questionnaires for a direct survey conducted from April 1st, 2023, to May 1st, 2023. Additionally, the authors utilized the following data analysis methods: (1) evaluating scale reliability using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, (2) exploratory factor analysis (EFA), and (3) multiple regression model analysis. The research findings indicate that there are two components of perceived corporate social responsibility that impact employee commitment to job retention, namely responsibility towards the government and responsibility towards customers, with responsibility towards the government having a greater influence. These research results provide a valuable foundation for SMEs in the Mekong Delta to consult and develop strategies for perceiving social responsibility in order to enhance loyalty, commitment, and retention among employees and the organization. This, in turn, helps businesses retain human resources and maintain sustainable business performance.

Keywords: Social responsibility; employee retention and engagement; small and medium enterprises; Mekong Delta.

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1.- Introduction

Corporate social responsibility has a positive impact on business results, effective implementation of corporate social responsibility is an important prerequisite for the success of a business, because the implementation of corporate social responsibility brings great benefits such as increasing revenue and labor productivity, reducing employee turnover, attracting skilled workers or improving competitiveness. and expand consumption markets (Giang Cao Tran, 2017; Meyer et al., 2002; Peterson, 2004; Tajfel and Turner, 1986). Corporate social responsibility is considered a "guideline" for businesses to develop sustainably in the new trend. In an increasingly technological world, the trend of internationalization and global integration, the deepening and deepening trade relations between countries and regions, besides the opportunities, businesses are face fierce competition and challenges. That is even more evident for small and medium-sized enterprises, which have not been able to create solid competitive advantages, have to face the fierce difficulties of the integration market.

According to the General Statistics Office, by the end of 2022, there are nearly 54,000 small and medium enterprises in the Mekong Delta, accounting for about 97% of the total number of businesses operating in the region. Small and medium enterprises contribute to the region's GDP on average about 70%/year and solve for 51.0% of labor in the enterprise sector in general. In the Mekong Delta, there is a lot of potential for development in the fields of industry, commerce, services, agriculture and fisheries. Those advantages have created favorable conditions for small and medium enterprises to form and develop. In fact, small and medium enterprises are facing difficulties in

terms of capital, management capacity, financial management, and the ability to withstand crises and economic downturns. Therefore, it is required that businesses are always flexible to change and adapt to integration in addition to timely support policies from the government.

With the number of enterprises operating in the Mekong Delta mostly small and medium-sized enterprises, the assessment of the implementation of corporate social responsibility of this group of enterprises for the employee retention strategy employees, the key nucleus of the business, this is certainly a practice that needs to be surveyed and measured. Because of that, a comprehensive overview and assessment of corporate social responsibility for employee engagement in small and medium-sized enterprises in the Mekong Delta aims to find the effect of perceived corporate social responsibility on employee engagement in small and medium enterprises. From here, the recommendations are proposed to contribute to promoting the engagement and retention of employees in small and medium enterprises in the Mekong Delta, which is necessary and has practical significance today.

2.- THEORETICAL BASIS AND RESEARCH MODEL

2.1. Theoretical basis

Around the world, the concept of corporate social responsibility is unfamiliar in many developing countries (Kwesi. A and Kwasi. D, 2015). In 1970, the economist Milton Friedman (1970) argued that: Corporate social responsibility is to contribute to increasing profits, Friedman argued that the sole goal of companies is to increase profits for the companies. their shareholders. In addition, according to the definition of the World Bank (2003), social responsibility is: "commitment of enterprises to contribute to sustainable economic development, commitment to work with employees, their families, the local community and society at large to improve their quality of life in ways that are both good for business and good for development".

Thus, the term corporate social responsibility has a long history of development in the world (Carroll, 2009). In 1953, researcher Bowen (1953) mentioned corporate social responsibility in the book "Social responsibility of business people", corporate social responsibility is not a new field of business. research, but recently corporate social responsibility is receiving attention and interest among the world's leading companies, universities, researchers, media, governments and organizations. non-government. However, nowadays more and more businesses think that a business cannot do well if it only maximizes profits that they need to have obligations to stakeholders and more. Corporate social responsibility is not only necessary for businesses but also for customers, employees and society. Good implementation of corporate social responsibility contributes to improving the image and reputation of enterprises, enhancing the competitiveness of enterprises. Not only that, corporate social responsibility is also an effective way to attract and retain talented people, corporate social responsibility has a relationship between employees' awareness of corporate social

responsibility and corporate social responsibility. career with a commitment to long-term employment (Stephen et al., 2007).

The commitment and attachment of employees to the perception of corporate social responsibility is argued based on social identity theory (Henry Tajfel and John Turner, 1986). Social identity theory refers to individuals who consider themselves members of a social category (Turner 1985; Tajfel and Turner 1986; Hogg and Abrams 1988). In 1990, the research group of Alen and Meyer (1990) reported that the three main components of cognition are social classification, social identity and social comparison. Individuals wish to maintain a positive social identity by maintaining the group's favorable social position relative to relevant outside groups. In 2002, Meyer et al. (2002) added that the theory of affective commitment is related to labor turnover and intention to leave the organization, but in fact there exists a strong relationship. The relationship between emotional commitment and employees' desired outcomes includes work performance, stress, health, and conflict outside of work (Meyer et al., 2002). According to Meyer, corporate social responsibility is an integral part of the employee's work experience, and employees' perceptions of the company's ethics, values and social responsiveness play an important role in forming emotional commitment. As such, corporate social responsibility contributes positively to an organization's reputation. Employees tend to have a stronger emotional identification with the organization (Peterson, 2004). Corporate social engagement results have a positive contribution to employee emotional commitment, as employees are likely to identify with organizations that have positive values in carrying out their social responsibilities. businesses, as employees benefit from association with organizations with a positive image (Peterson, 2004).

Today, there is a lot of research on corporate social responsibility with employee engagement. For example, in the study of Maignan et al. (1999) based on the four-component model of Carroll (1979) and studied the influence of each component on the employee's attachment to the enterprise, using the scale. The measurement includes 18 components to measure the perception of corporate social responsibility and a 7-component scale to measure organizational commitment. Research has proven that most components of corporate social responsibility have a positive and strong impact on employee engagement. An argument by Peterson (2004) shows that all four components of corporate social responsibility have a positive effect on employee's intention to stick, employees have belief in the benefits of social activities. The higher the company's association, the higher the level of engagement. The ethical factors are the strongest influence on the employees, he thinks that the companies that value business ethics will treat their employees accordingly. kindest way.

Another study was conducted by Imran Ali et al (2010) on 371 employees working in Pakistan. The study shows a strong influence of all components in the employees' perception of corporate social responsibility on employee engagement, and the study also shows the perceived social responsibility of employees. also positively affect the performance of the business. Research by Choi and Yu (2014), shows the civic behavior of employees in the organization and the performance of the organization.

In addition, discussing the perception of corporate social responsibility with employee engagement, in the study of Osveh et al (2015) on the influence of corporate social responsibility perception on employee engagement, he also defines engagement here as the willingness to participate in the organization's activities and long-term commitment to the organization. The study is based on the theory of Carroll (1979) and surveyed over 220 employees of a second largest automobile company in Iran. The results of this study show that only two components of corporate social responsibility, ethics and philanthropy, have a positive effect on employee engagement while the other two hypotheses are "positive influence on employee engagement of the economic and legal sectors" is not satisfied. Explaining the refutation of these two hypotheses, the author argues that the company's profit is not a motivating factor for employees because their salary is always fixed whether the company does well or not. Moreover, in some cases the growth of the company means more work and employees may have to work overtime, even though they will receive additional remuneration but it does not compensate the effort they put in. If the company does not have high profit and can't afford to pay them, they are ready to leave to find a new company, it is also the habit of workers in Iran that makes the job hopping rate of this country very high.

In the Romanian study, Simona Vinerean et al (2013) "Modeling employee satisfaction in relation to corporate social responsibility practices and attracting and retaining top talent". The author tested and came to a conclusion that accepts three hypotheses (1) corporate social responsibility has a positive impact on employee satisfaction, (2) corporate social responsibility has a positive impact on employee satisfaction positively affects the attractiveness and commitment of employees, (3) The attractiveness and commitment of employees have an impact on employee satisfaction through employee surveys working at the top 10 large multinational companies in Romania, all of these companies are currently committed to and well implementing corporate social responsibility activities in their businesses.

In Vietnam, corporate social responsibility has not been widely disseminated from theory to practice, most scholars have only conducted research projects on corporate social responsibility for about 15 years. come back here. Among them, not many authors study corporate social responsibility in small and medium enterprises. Therefore, in this section, the author not only introduces the research on social responsibility for small and medium-sized enterprises, but also reviews typical studies on issues surrounding the topic of awareness and implementation of social responsibility. corporate society. With this same argument, the study of Le Thanh Tiep (2018) with "The influence of social responsibility and employee engagement on corporate performance: A case study of southern enterprises". Through many analytical models from basic to advanced such as: exploratory factor analysis (EFA), confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), and linear structural model analysis (SEM). Analytical data were surveyed from 1000 samples of employees and managers working at 500 working for foreign-invested enterprises and 500 being domestic private enterprises. The analysis results of all 13 hypotheses mentioned are accepted, namely: (H1) Social responsibility towards the Government; (H2) Social responsibility towards related parties; (H3) Social responsibility towards

employees; (H4) Social responsibility towards employees has an impact on corporate social responsibility; (H5) Emotional attachment has a positive impact on employee engagement in enterprises; (H6) Engagement for retention has a positive impact on employee engagement in the enterprise; (H7) Ethical commitment has a positive impact on employee engagement in the enterprise; (H8) social responsibility has a positive impact on employee engagement; (H9) corporate social responsibility has a positive impact on organizational identity; (H10) Employee engagement in the enterprise has a positive impact on organizational identity; (H11) Corporate social responsibility has a positive impact on corporate performance; (H12) Employee engagement has a positive impact on business performance; (H13) Organizational identity has a positive impact on firm performance.

Another study by Le Thanh Ha (2009), has given the concepts and principles of implementing social responsibility, notably the principles of ensuring human rights: (1) Businesses need to support support and respect the protection of internationally recognized human rights; (2) Businesses need to ensure that they are not involved in the infringement of human rights. Principles of labor standards: (3) enterprises respect freedom of association and recognize the right to collective bargaining; (4) Elimination of all forms of forced or compulsory labor; (5) Effectively eliminate child labor; (6) Elimination of discrimination related to employment and occupation.

Finally, the study of Le Thi Thu Thuy (2013), using qualitative analysis methods to assess the status of social responsibility implementation according to the Carroll model, the author has clarified the challenges for businesses in Vietnam when implementing social responsibility and the benefits from the implementation of social responsibility, thereby giving some suggestions on basic solutions to raise the awareness of implementing social responsibility in Vietnam.

2.2. Research models

Based on the research overview and theoretical framework, the research model is proposed as follows: (Figure 1)

Figure 1.
Author's proposed research model

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1. Scale development

In which, the scale used to measure concepts in the research model is inherited from previous studies.

Table 1.
Scale of research concepts

Encode	Research concept	Number of variables	Reference source
L Q	Social responsibility towards stakeholders	6	Choi & Yu (2013); Expert discussion
C P	Social responsibility towards the Government	4	Simona Vinerean & cộng sự (2013); Expert discussion
N V	Social responsibility for Employees	6	Peterson (2004); Expert discussion
K H	Social responsibility for Customers	4	Choi & Yu (2013); Expert discussion
G B	Employee engagement and retention	3	Peterson (2004); Expert discussion

Source: The author's data collection and analysis results

3.2. Research stages

3.2.1. Qualitative research

At the preliminary research stage, the author uses qualitative research methods with target group discussion techniques. Specifically, the author uses convenient sampling method, selecting 10 employees and 10 managers who are leaders of enterprises located in provinces and regions in the Mekong Delta. All interviews were in the form of face-to-face interviews with a duration of 30 to 60 minutes, with an average of 45 minutes. Interview period is February 2023 to March 2023. The objective of the employee group interview is to evaluate and edit the content of observations and models, research hypotheses, methods of measuring variables and model results. The objective of interviewing the target group is managers to find out, their views on social responsibility for employee retention and engagement in their business. Also, investigate their level of understanding and contribution to the observations in the research scale.

3.2.2. Quantitative research

At the quantitative research stage, the author uses the non-probability sampling method, which is convenience sampling, which is applied when implementing sampling, whereby a list of small and medium-sized enterprises is classified by type of industry business of the enterprise used to conduct the survey. Survey subjects are employees at small and medium-sized enterprises in the Mekong Delta in order to verify the accuracy and suitability of the model, assess the reliability of the scale, variables, and observations input and remove inappropriate indicators. Data were collected by distributing questionnaires to a direct survey for the period from April 1, 2023 to May 1, 2023, with an expected sample size of 250.

3.3. Data analysis

- Testing the scale: Using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient to evaluate the quality of the construction scale. The scale is evaluated as good quality when: (1) Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the population is greater than 0.6; and (2) The correlation coefficient - the sum of the observed variables is greater than 0.3 (Corrected Item - Total Correlation), (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994).

- Exploratory factor analysis (EFA): helps to extract factors for further analysis. Factor loading coefficients are the criterion to ensure the practical significance of EFA. This coefficient greater than 0.3 is considered the minimum level, greater than 0.4 is considered important, greater than 0.5 is considered to be of practical significance (Hair et al., 1998). In this study, in order to improve the practicality and reliability of the research results, the author only selects the factors with the transfer coefficient greater than 0.5, the Kaiser-Mayer-Olkin (KMO) has the highest value. large value (between 0.5 and 1) and the total variance extracted is greater than 0.5 to ensure the explanatory content of the factors obtained from the results of EFA analysis. Principal Component Analysis method and Varimax rotation will be used in this study to extract key factors.

- Regression model analysis method to find the influence of perceived corporate social responsibility on employee engagement in small and medium enterprises in the Mekong Delta.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. Research sample information

The research sample was selected by non-probability sampling method, which is convenient sampling, stratified relatively according to provinces and localities in order

to increase the representativeness of the research sample including Can Tho City, Dong Thap Province, Vinh Long, An Giang, Kien Giang, Tien Giang and classified by type of business lines of enterprises. The survey unit in the study was identified as employees in small and medium enterprises.

Table 2.
Distribution of the research sample

Research sample structure		Number of survey samples	Number of samples collected	Ratio %
Local investigation	Can Tho city	50	46	20.0
	Dong Thap Province	50	47	20.5
	Vinh Long Province	40	37	16.1
	An Giang Province	40	36	15.7
	Kien Giang Province	40	37	16.1
	Tien Giang Province	30	26	11.6
Business	Agriculture forestry seafood	85	77	33.6
	Industry and construction	85	79	34.4
	Trade and services	80	73	32.0
Total		250	229	100

Source: The author's data collection and analysis results

4.2. Evaluate the reliability of the scale

The first study to perform Cronbach's Alpha test is to analyze and evaluate the reliability of the scale (Table 3). According to Nunnally & Bernstein (1994), the value of Cronbach's Alpha coefficient ≥ 0.60 is an acceptable scale in terms of reliability; Corrected item-total correlation coefficient ≥ 0.30 indicates that the variable meets the requirements.

Through the test results of 5 scales, there are 4 scales including LQ, CP, NV, GB all meeting the requirements for testing. There are no offending variables compared to Cronbach's Alpha results of each scale. Particularly, the KH scale with the KH1 variable was rejected because it did not meet the test requirements because it had a Corrected item-total correlation < 0.30 . Therefore, the KH scale with 3 remaining variables was

retested and met the test requirements. The summary of the test results is shown in Table 3.

The author analyzed two conditions when performing Cronbach's Alpha test: Cronbach's Alpha coefficient ≥ 0.60 and Corrected item-total correlation ≥ 0.3 . However, in this test it is also necessary to consider Cronbach's Alpha coefficient if the variable type (Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted) of each variable with Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, if this coefficient is larger, the variable must be removed from the model. For example, the scale of social responsibility to stakeholders (LQ), in this scale, there are 6 observed variables: LQ1, LQ2, LQ3, LQ4, LQ5, LQ6. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of all 6 observed variables with the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient = 0.800, if it is larger, it must be discarded.

Table 3.
Summary of Cronbach's Alpha values of variables

Variable	Symbol	Coefficient Cronbach's Alpha	Evaluate result
Social responsibility towards stakeholders	L Q	0.800	Accept
Social responsibility towards the Government	C P	0.928	Accept
Social responsibility for Employees	N V	0.785	Accept
Social responsibility for Customers	K H	0.700	Accept
Employee engagement and retention	G B	0.660	Accept

Source: The author's data collection and analysis results

4.3. Exploratory factor analysis EFA

After evaluating the reliability of the scale, the study continued to perform exploratory factor analysis (EFA). The condition that the observed variables have statistical significance has the coefficient of KMO in the range from 0.5 to 1; Barlett's test has sig value. less than 0.05; Eigenvalue ≥ 1 and total variance extracted $\geq 50\%$. However, the results of the rotation factor have the variable KH4 with the factor loading coefficient appearing in 2 groups of factors and the difference in the loading coefficient between the two factors is less than 0.3. Therefore, the KH4 variable is eliminated and the performance results are shown in Table 4. The results of Table 4 show that the KH4 observed variable is removed, because it is uploaded in both factors.

Next, the study performed Bartlett's Test of Sphericity to examine the correlation matrix with the hypothesis that the correlation matrix is a unit matrix, if the Bartlett test has P-Value < 0.05 then the above hypothesis can be rejected, that is, the variables are related. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy (KMO) test is an indicator used to consider the adequacy of factor analysis. The value of KMO must be from 0.5 or more, according to Kaiser (1974), KMO value ≥ 0.90 is very good, KMO ≥ 0.80 is good, KMO ≥ 0.70 is okay, KMO ≥ 0.60 is okay, KMO ≥ 0.50 is bad and KMO < 0.50 is not acceptable. According to the research results, the value of KMO = 0.754 satisfies the condition of $0.5 \leq KMO \leq 1$, so independent factor analysis is consistent with the actual data.

Testing the correlation between observed variables (Bartlett's Test): The study hypothesizes H0: the correlation level of the variables is zero. The results of Bartlett's test have the value Sig.=0.000 < 0.05, so the hypothesis H0 is rejected. Therefore, the observed variables are correlated with each other in each factor group (Table 4).

Table 4.
Exploratory factor analysis results EFA

Observed variables	Factor			
	1	2	3	4
CP2	0.916			
CP1	0.900			
CP3	0.854			
CP4	0.854			
LQ4		0.785		
LQ1		0.760		
LQ5		0.757		
LQ2		0.755		
LQ3		0.720		
LQ6		0.508		
NV6			0.760	
NV1			0.750	
NV2			0.740	
NV5			0.676	
NV4			0.652	
NV3			0.525	

KH3				0.821
KH2				0.667
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin:0.753***				
Cumulative variance: 62,009				
Sig: 0,000				

Source: The author's data collection and analysis results

4.4. Analysis of regression model

Performing regression test of adjusted R² = 0.845, which means that in 100% of the variation of the dependent variable, 84.5% of the variation due to the impact is explained by the independent variables, the rest 15.4% due to random error or other factors outside the model (Table 5). Standardized regression results describe the influencing factors of social responsibility perception on employee engagement. With the VIF values of all independent variables being < 2, the model shows no multicollinearity. The sig value < 0.05 shows that the model is statistically significant. The adjusted R² index 0.845 means that in 100% of the variation of the dependent variable, 84.5 of the fluctuations are due to the effects explained by the independent variables, the remaining 15.3% are due to random errors. natural or other factors not mentioned in the model (19.3% or 19.5%).

Table 5.
Results of regression analysis of the model

Variable	Un normalized regression coefficients	Normalized regression coefficients	Sig.	VIF
(Constant)	0.253			
CP	0.375***	0,441	0.000	1.381
LQ	0.000	0.000	0.993	1.006
NV	0.010	0.011	0.694	1.057
KH	0.531***	0.608	0.000	1.395
R² correction	0.845			
F (Anova)	312.694***			
Durbin-Watson	1.551			

*Note: *** is 1% statistically significant, ** is 5% statistically significant, * is 10% statistically significant.*

Source: The author's data collection and analysis results

4.5. Discussing research results

The social responsibility factor for the Government (CP) has an unnormalized regression coefficient $B = 0.375$ and has a positive sign (+), so it has a positive relationship with the dependent variable, satisfying the sign expectation. Assuming constant factors, if the social responsibility towards the Government increases by 1 unit, it will increase the retention and retention (GB) of the average employee by 0.375 units. The standardized regression coefficient of the factor Social responsibility for the Government (CP) is $\beta = 0.441$, so this is the factor with the second strongest impact on employee engagement and retention at small and medium enterprises in the Mekong Delta. This result is consistent with the study of Maignan et al (1999), Peterson (2004), Turker (2009b), Choi and Yu (2013), Simona Vinerean et al (2013).

This result is consistent with reality because any business, including small and medium-sized enterprises, when starting a business must comply with the Government's regulations. The State has the responsibility to codify social and ethical rules into documents so that businesses can pursue their economic goals within the framework of the regulations in an equitable manner and meet the basic standards and values established by the Government social expectations of businesses such as protecting employees and customers and stakeholders. A business that deceives public authorities, or commits tax evasion or other violations of the law, may make employees no longer proud to be a member of the business they work for and this will reduce the engagement and retention of these employees at SMEs in the Mekong Delta.

The factor of social responsibility for stakeholders (XH) has an unstandardized regression coefficient $B = 0.000$ and has a positive sign (+), so it has a positive relationship with the variables of employee attachment and retention members (GB), which satisfies the sign expectation. However, the Sig value of the factor of social responsibility for stakeholders (XH) is equal to 0.993, so it can be concluded that the variable of social responsibility for stakeholders (XH) has no effect on employee engagement and retention (GB) with SMEs in the Mekong Delta. Although, social responsibility towards stakeholders (Social) was found to be a factor that has a strong influence on employee engagement and retention in previous studies (Peterson, 2004; Turker, 2009b; Choi and Yu, 2013).

However, the results of this study have not provided strong evidence on the influence of social responsibility for stakeholders (social) on the attachment and retention (GB) of employees at small and medium enterprises in the Mekong Delta. This shows that SMEs in the Mekong Delta are not profitable enough to be able to allocate capital for social activities and support community development in the Mekong Delta. In addition, small and medium enterprises in the Mekong Delta are not aware of the importance of social responsibility for stakeholders in building corporate culture.

Factor of social responsibility for employees (NV): The factor has an unstandardized regression coefficient $B = 0.010$ and has a positive sign (+), so it has a

positive relationship with the variable of employee attachment and retention members (GB), which satisfies the sign expectation. However, the Sig value of the Social Responsibility Factor for employees (NV) is equal to 0.694, so it can be concluded that the variable social responsibility for employees (NV) has no effect on the engagement and retention (GB) of employees with SMEs in the Mekong Delta. Turker (2009b) suggests that an organization's internal environment can be a precursor to organizational commitment. Good working conditions include career opportunities, or organizational equity policies that affect employees' level of commitment to the organization. In fact, such a relationship is between social responsibility to employees and employee engagement and retention with the organization related to career development, training opportunities or equal rights of employees. These needs are identified according to the higher order needs for self-esteem and self-actualization in Maslow's classification. But the reality in Vietnam shows that the majority of small and medium-sized enterprises do not have an employee training and development strategy associated with the specific vision and goals of the business (Nguyen Thi Thanh Binh, 2018). Therefore, employees consider the social responsibility factor to employees (NV) not important for the attachment and retention in small and medium enterprises in the Mekong Delta.

The factor of social responsibility for customers (KH) has an unnormalized regression coefficient $B = 0.531$ and has a positive sign (+), so it has a positive relationship with the dependent variable, satisfying the sign expectation. With the assumption of constant factors, if social responsibility to customers increases by 1 unit, it will help to increase employee engagement and retention by an average of 0.531 units. The factor of social responsibility for customers (KH) has a standardized regression coefficient of $\beta = 0.608$, so this is the factor that has the strongest impact on employee engagement and retention in small and medium enterprises in the Mekong Delta.

According to Turker (2009b), customers are the source of the business's revenue and the success of the business depends heavily on the customers. Therefore, businesses often maintain good relationships with customers. If SMEs deceive customers by providing poor quality products and services, or products and services do not match their original description, employees of these small and medium enterprises may feel ashamed for these behaviors of the business and reduce the level of commitment to the business. In contrast, small and medium-sized businesses that provide quality products and services and live up to their initial description of commitments to customers, employees will feel proud to be a member of the organization. This will increase employee engagement and retention with SMEs in the Mekong Delta. This result is consistent with the study of Maignan et al. (1999), Peterson (2004), Brammer et al. (2005), Turker (2009b), Choi and Yu (2013), Simona Vinerean et al (2013) .

5. Conclusions and management implications

In any business, the most important asset of the enterprise is the human resources, it is difficult to find a human resource that meets the standards of qualifications and skills suitable to the corporate culture. It is more difficult to get them long-term with the business. Therefore, with the aim of the study on employee engagement and retention in the enterprise, it is based on the perception of corporate social responsibility. Regression results show that responsibility to the government and responsibility to customers have a significant influence on the engagement and retention of employees working at small and medium enterprises in the Mekong Delta. Long. Therefore, the author proposes the following recommendations:

Firstly, about the responsibility to the Government: small and medium enterprises need to comply with the law because operating within the legal framework is an important factor for the sustainable development of businesses. That includes small and medium enterprises. Businesses need to fulfill their responsibilities and obligations (insurance, tax,...), business activities need to be transparent, clear and not do fraudulent business. Besides, small and medium enterprises should also increase activities for the community.

Secondly, regarding responsibility to customers: customers are users of goods and services of enterprises, so the success of businesses depends greatly on customers. Therefore, businesses must not only understand and perform their social responsibilities well to customers, but also understand responsible consumption behavior, because consumers can use their power to ensure corporate social responsibility. Therefore, small and medium-sized businesses must protect the interests of their customers and are responsible for compensating customers for damage caused by defects in their products or failure to ensure a reasonable level of safety for their customers. client. Besides, businesses do not have advertising acts that cause confusion for customers; consumer harassment behavior; consumer coercion...

In addition, the research results, although not providing strong evidence to support the influence of social responsibility on stakeholders and social responsibility on employees, small and medium enterprises It is also necessary to pay attention to these two aspects to increase employee engagement and retention.

Bibliographic references

- Aguilera, R. V., Rupp, D. E., Williams, C. A., & Ganapathi, J. (2007). Putting the S back in corporate social responsibility: A multi-level theory of social change in organizations. **Academy of Management Review**, 32(3), 836-863.
- Anderson, E., & Oliver, R. L. (1987). Perspectives on behavior-based versus outcome-based salesforce control systems. **Journal of Marketing**, 51(2), 76-88.

- Armstrong, M. (2006). **A handbook of human resource management practice** (10th ed.). London, UK: Kogan Page Limited.
- Borman, W. C., & Brush, D. H. (1993). More progress toward a taxonomy of managerial performance requirements. **Human Performance**, 6(1), 1-21.
- Brammer, S., Millington, A., & Rayton, B. (2007). The contribution of corporate social responsibility to organizational commitment. **International Journal of Human Resource Management**, 18(10), 1701-1719.
- Brammer, S., & Millington, A. (2005), Corporate reputation and philanthropy: An empirical analysis, **Journal of Business Ethics**, 61, pp 29-44.
- Bowen, H. R. (1953), **Social responsibilities of the businessman**, New York: Harper và Row.
- Carroll, A.B. (1979), The three dimensional conceptual model of corporate performance, **Academy of management review** 1979, Vol 4, No 4, pp 497 - 505.
- Carroll, A.B. (1991), The pyramid of corporate social responsibility: Toward the moral management of organizational stakeholders, **Business Horizons** 34, pp 39-48.
- Carroll, Archie B. 2009, A History of Corporate Social Responsibility Concepts and Practices. In *The Oxford Handbook of Corporate Social Responsibility*, **Oxford: Oxford University Press**, pp. 19-46.
- Choi and Yu, (2014), **The Influence of Perceived Corporate Sustainability Practices on Employees and organizational Performance**, Jangxi university of Finance and Economics, *Sustainability* 2014, 6(1), pp 348-364.
- Chu Thanh Hai (2019), Developing small and medium-sized enterprises in Vietnam today, **Vietnam Journal of Social Sciences**, No. 11,2019.
- Le Thanh Ha (2009), Corporate social responsibility in the context of Vietnam's accession to WTO and international economic integration, Science and Technology Publishing House.
- Le Thi Thu Thuy (2013), Implementing social responsibility - Benefits for businesses, **Economic & Development Magazine**, No. 216, pp 01.
- Matten, D., & Moon, J. (2008). "Implicit" and "explicit" CSR: A conceptual framework for a comparative understanding of corporate social responsibility. **Academy of Management Review**, 33(2), 404-424.
- Maignan I., and Ferrell O. C. (2001), Antecedents and benefits of corporate citizenship: An Investigation of French Business, **Journal of Business Research**, 51, pp 37-51.
- Mowday, T. R., Steers, M. R., and Porter, W. L., (1979), The measurement of organizational commitment, **Journal of Vocational Behavior**, 14(2), pp 224-247.
- Meyer, J. P., Allen, N. J., (1991), A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment, **Human Resource Management Review**, 1(1), pp 61-89.

- Nguyen Thi Le Tram, (2016), Human resource management in small and medium enterprises: Current situation and some recommendations, **Financial Journal**, period 3.
- Kaiser, H. F., & Rice, J. (1974), Little jiffy, mark IV. **Educational and psychological measure- ment**, 34(1), 111-117.
- Turker, D. (2009a), Measuring corporate social responsibility: A scale development study, **Journal of business ethics**, 85(4), 411-427.
- Turker, D. (2009b), How corporate social responsibility influences organizational commitment, **Journal of Business ethics**, 89(2), 189-204.
- Turker, D. (2008). How corporate social responsibility influences organizational commitment. **Journal of Business Ethics**, 89(2), 189-204. doi:10.1007/s10551-008-9993-8
- Vansteenkiste, M. (2010). **Motivational profiles from a self-determination theory perspective**. Paper present at the 4th Conference on Self-Determination Theory (SDT), Ghent, Belgium.
- Yousaf, A., Yang, H., & Sanders, K. (2015). Effects of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation on task and contextual performance of Pakistani professionals: The mediating role of commitment foci. **Journal of Managerial Psychology**, 30(2), 133-155.
- Williams, L. J., & Anderson, S. E. (1991). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment as predictors of organizational citizenship and in-role behaviors. **Journal of Management**, 17(3), 601-617. doi:10.1177/014920639101700305